

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN BEHAVIOURAL PROBLEM AND EMOTIONAL MATURITY AMONG ADOLESCENTS

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ABSTRACT:

The aim of the research was to study the relationship between behavioural problem and emotional maturity among adolescents. A total sample of 100 students was selected from two intermediate schools of Haridwar district, Uttarakhand. Emotional Maturity scale developed by Dr. Yashvir. Singh & Dr Mahesh Bhargava (2012) for measuring emotional maturity & Problem Behavioural Survey Schedule prepared by Dr. S. Venkatesan (2015) were applied for data collection. Correlation was calculated. Results of the study revealed that (1) there is negative relationship between externalizing behavioural problem and emotional stability; (2) there is negative co-relation between externalizing problem behavior and emotional progression; (3) relationship between internalizing behavioural problem and emotional stability is negative; (4) internalizing behavioural problem is negatively related with emotional progression; (5) relationship between internalizing behavioural problem and social adjustment is negatively correlated; (6) intense problem behavior is negatively correlated with emotional stability as well as with emotional progression; (8) total behavioural problem is negative correlated with both emotional stability and emotional progression.

KEY WORDS: Behavioural problem, Emotional maturity, Adolescents.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Adolescent is the period of transformation from childhood to adulthood. In this stage, there is rapid physical growth and development as well as upheavals of psychological changes. In addition to daily life they have to tackle difficult situation due to demands of digital world. Problem behavior is noticed in adolescents. Krupa Hiremath & et al. (2008) stated 9-18% of adolescents were found with difficult behavior. Boys had significantly more externalizing problems while girls had significantly more of internalizing problem [4]. Woo & et al. (2007) found that boys scored high on the social problems, thought problems, attention problems, delinquency, aggressiveness and externalizing

problems [11]. Bongers & et al. (2003), Mesman et al. (2001) reported that boys exhibited more externalizing problems [2][5].

Emotion plays a crucial part in human being life. It helps individuals to reach one's goal. Emotional mature person can effectively deal with his environment. So one's degree of emotional maturity is one of the biggest elements in determining one's ability to manage. Emotional mature person have more constructive attitude towards life. Emotionally mature adolescents can face their problems effectively without being depressed, stressed, addicted to drugs and committing suicide. Bansal (2013) in his study found that there was a significant difference between classroom behavior and emotional maturity of normal and learning disabled children [1]. Sasi Kumar Roja & Fathima (2013) stated that there is positive relationship between emotional maturity and self concept [7]. Geeta S. Pastey and Vijaya Laxmi (2006) revealed in their study that adolescents with high emotional maturity have significant high stress and self concept when compared to those with low emotional maturity [3]. Suman Nehru (2014) reported in her study that there is no significant relationship between the adjustment and emotional maturity [6]. In this study, investigator wants to see the association between emotional maturity and problem behavior, as there is dearth of study on it.

II. OBJECTIVES:

- To know the interrelationship between emotional maturity and behavioural problems.
- To compare between emotional maturity and dimensions of behavioural problem.

III. HYPOTHESIS:

Emotional maturity will be negatively correlated with behavioural problems and its dimensions.

IV. RESEARCH DESIGN:

2x2 Factorial design was used where two levels of group (rural and urban) and two sexes (Boys and Girls) were matched together to yield four conditions.

V. SAMPLE:

100 students of eleventh class, out of which 50 students from rural school and 50 students from urban school of Haridwar district, Uttarakhand. From urban and rural students were further divided 25 boys and 25 girls respectively by stratified random sampling technique.

VI. TOOLS TO BE USED:

The following fairly developed and standardized tools were used i.e Emotional Maturity scale prepared by Dr. Yashvir. Singh & Dr. Mahesh. Bhargava (2012) for measuring emotional maturity. Problem Behavioural Survey Schedule prepared by Dr. S. Venkatesan (2015)

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOLS:

Tools were described below-

(1) Problem behavior survey schedule:

The PBBSS consists of 100 items grouped under 11 domains as given below in Table

Distribution of domain under PBSS

Sr.No.	Domains	Items
1	Violent-destructive behavior	16
2	Temper tantrum	4
3	Misbehavior with others	14
4	Self injurious behavior	11
5	Repetitive behavior	9
6	Odd behavior	10
7	Hyperactivity	3
8	Rebellious behavior	6
9	Antisocial behavior	14
10	Fears	4
11	Any other	9
	Total	100

The eleven domains of problem behaviours are also grouped into two categories: Externalising (E) and Internalising (I) problem behaviours. Externalizing behavioural problem behavior contains temper tantrum,

misbehavior with others, rebellious behavior and antisocial behavior. Internalizing behavioural problem includes violent-destructive behavior, self injurious behavior, odd behavior, hyperactivity and fear.[10] The inter-observer reliability for PBSS estimated using Pearson’s Correlation between ratings was $r=0.911(p:<0.001)$. Cronbach’s alpha correlation coefficients of reliability between domains varied between 0.18 and 0.89.

(2) Emotional Maturity Scale:

This scale consisted of five components that are (a) Emotional stability,(b)Emotional progression, (c) Social adjustment, (d) Personality integration, (e) Independence. Emotional maturity Scale has a total of 48 statements under the five categories. In test-retest method the reliability of the scale was 0.75. Validity of the scale was calculated by product moment correlation between external criteria and total score of EMS, which was 0.64.

VIII. COLLECTION OF DATA:

The investigator visited the schools personally and administered the tools with a request to give their responses against all the items of the tools separately. They were not only explained the purpose and significance of the study. They were given assurance that their information would be kept confidential and utilized for research purpose only. The students showed keen interest to go through each item sincerely and carefully. The investigator told the students to put tick mark (✓) against any of the choices in emotional maturity scale. In problem behavioural schedule, the investigator had read out each item on the tool to verify whether that particular problem behavior is indeed ‘present’ or ‘absent’ in a given child. If present the next level of exploration involves enquiring whether that particular problem behavior is present in the given child ‘occasionally’ or ‘frequently’ as perceived or reported by the teacher. According to the response the investigator put tick mark (✓) against appropriate place. [10][9]

IX. SCORING PROCEDURE:

(a) scoring procedure of problem behaviour schedule:

The scoring of each child on the PBSS is carried out on two calculation: ‘Frequency score’ (FS) based on presence or absence of given problem behaviors; and the ‘Intensity/Severity score (I/SS).’ The former is marked as ‘present’ or ‘absent’. While the ‘absent’ is always scored as zero, the ‘present’ items are scored as ‘present occasionally’ (score: 1) or ‘present frequently’ (Score: two). Thus, the maximum possible Frequency Score (FS)

on PBSS is 100 and Intensity/ severity score (I/SS) is 200 for a given child. The PBSS also facilitates for each student another 'Directionality Score' (DS) in terms of 'internalising' (DS-I) and /or 'externalizing' (DS-E) patterns of problem behavior. Further, on the PBSS, one can also deduce the deviation score of problem behavior for a given individual to be interpreted as per against available norms.[10]

(b)Scoring procedure of Emotional Maturity scale:

Emotional Maturity Scale is a self-reporting five point scale. If the answer is very much a score of 5 is given; for much 4; for undecided 3; and for probably 2 and for negative answer of never a score of 1 is to be answered. Therefore, total score on the scale is indicative of emotional maturity whereas the greater the total score on the scale is expressed in terms of emotional immaturity.[9]

X. STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED:

Correlation was applied for the purpose of the study..

XI. RESULTS & TABULATION:

Table no.1: Correlation of Matrix of total sample

Dimension of variables,→	ES	EP	SA	PI	I	Total EM	DSE	DSI	FS	ISS	Total BP
ES	1.00	0.70	0.60	0.67	0.58	0.82	-0.002	-0.10	0.06	-0.11	-0.05
EP		1.00	0.73	0.75	0.69	0.90	-0.001	-0.18	0.07	-0.12	-0.06
SA			1.00	0.79	0.71	0.89	0.07	-0.08	-0.06	0.10	0.05
PI				1.00	0.69	0.90	0.08	0.07	0.04	0.09	0.10
I					1.00	0.83	0.19	0.04	0.13	0.12	0.19
Total EM						1.00	0.07	-0.06	0.05	0.01	0.04
DSE							1.00	0.61	0.46	0.74	0.93
DSI								1.00	0.51	0.60	0.85
FS									1.00	-0.13	0.54
ISS										1.00	0.77
Total BP											1.00

Table No1 shows correlation of total sample. It indicates that the co-efficient of correlation between emotional progression and emotional stability is 0.70 .That means interrelationship between emotional Progression and emotional stability is positive and substantial or marked relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between social adjustment and emotional stability is 0.60.It indicates that relationship between social adjustment and emotional stability is positive and marked. The correlation of coefficient between social adjustment and emotional progression is 0.73, which indicates connection between social adjustment and emotional progression is positive and high. The co-

efficient of correlation between personality integration and emotional stability is 0.67.It shows positive and substantial relationship between them. The co-efficient of correlation between personality integration and emotional progression is 0.75.That means there is positive and high correlation. The coefficient of correlation between personality integration and social adjustment is 0.79. It indicates there is positive and high correlation. The co-efficient of correlation between independence and emotional stability is 0.58. It shows that there is positive and marked relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between independence and emotional progression is 0.69.That means there is positive, substantial connection in them. The co-efficient of correlation of between independence and social adjustment is 0.71.It indicates that there is positive and substantial interrelation. The co-efficient of correlation between independence and personality integration is 0.69.That means there is positive, marked relationship between independence and personality integration. The co-efficient of correlation between total emotional maturity and emotional stability is 0.82. This indicates there is positive and very high correlation between emotional maturity and emotional stability. The co-efficient of correlation between whole emotional maturity and emotional progression is 0.90. It refers that com- parision between emotional maturity and emotional progression is positive and very high. The co-efficient of correlation between total emotional maturity and social adjustment is 0.89. It indicates that there is positive and very high association. The co-efficient of correlation between total emotional maturity and personality integration is 0.90. So, there is positive and high connection. The co-efficient of correlation between total emotional maturity and independence is 0.83.That means there is positive and very high relation. The co-efficient of correlation between directionality score in externalizing behavioral problem and emotional stability is -0.002.That means there is negative and very low. The co-efficient of correlation between externalizing problem behaviour and emotional progression is - 0.001.It refers that there is negative and very low association. The co-efficient of correlation between externalizing problem behavior and social adjustment is 0.07.That means there is positive and inconsequential connection. The co-efficient of correlation between directionality score of externalizing and personality integration is 0.08.That means there is positive but very low relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between directionality score of externalizing and independence is 0.19.That means there is positive but very low interrelationship. The co-efficient of correlation between directionality score of externalizing and total emotional

maturity is 0.07. That means there is positive but very low relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between directionality score of internalizing and emotional stability is - 0.10. That means there is adverse but very low relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between directionality score of internalizing and emotional progression -0.18. Therefore, there is nullifying and very minor interconnection. The co-efficient of correlation between internalizing and social adjustment is - 0.08. Hence, there is negative but very minute comparison. The co-efficient of correlation between directionality score of internalizing and personality integration is 0.07. Consequently, there is positive but unimportant relation. The co-efficient of correlation between internalizing and independence, is 0.04. As a deduction, there is positive but very low relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between directionality score of internalizing and total emotional maturity is -0.06. Thus there is negative but very low inter relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between directionality score of internalizing and externalizing is 0.61. From here, there is positive but marked relationship. Co-efficient of correlation between frequency score of problem behavior and emotional stability is 0.06. Thence, there is positive but imperceptible connection. The co-efficient of correlation between frequency score, a dimension of behavioural problem and emotional progression is 0.07. That means there is positive but very low relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between frequency score, a dimension of behavioural problem and social adjustment, a dimension of emotional maturity is -0.06. Thence, there is negative but very low connection. The co-efficient of correlation between frequency score, a dimension of behavioural problem and personality integration, a dimension of emotional maturity is 0.04. That means there is positive but very low relationship between frequency score of behavioral problem and social adjustment. The co-efficient of correlation between frequency score, a dimension of behavioural problem and independence, a dimension of emotional maturity is 0.13. That means there is positive but very low relationship between frequency score of behavioral problem and independence. The co-efficient of correlation between frequency score, a dimension of behavioural problem and total emotional maturity is 0.05. That means there is positive but very low relationship between frequency score of behavioral problem and emotional maturity. The co-efficient of correlation between frequency score, a dimension of behavioural problem and directionality score of externalizing, a dimension of behavioural problem is 0.46. That means there is positive but substantial relationship between frequency score of behavioral

problem and externalizing behavioural problem. The co-efficient of correlation between frequency score, a dimension of behavioural problem and directionality score of internalizing, a dimension of behavioural problem is 0.51. That states there is positive but marked relationship between frequency score of behavioral problem and internalizing behavioural problem. The co-efficient of correlation between intensity severe score, a dimension of behavioural problem and emotional stability, a dimension of emotional maturity is -0.11. That refers there is negative but negligible relationship between intensity severe score of behavioral problem and emotional stability. The co-efficient of correlation between intensity severe score and emotional progression is -0.12. That refers there is adverse but negligible relationship between intensity severe score of behavioral problem and emotional progression. The co-efficient of correlation between intensity severe score, a dimension of behavioural problem and social adjustment is -0.10. That refers there is positive but negligible inter-relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between intensity severe score and personality integration is 0.09. That indicates there is positive but negligible relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between intensity severe score and independence is 0.12. As a deduction, there is positive but negligible connection. The co-efficient of correlation between intensity severe score and total emotional maturity is 0.01. That states that there is positive but gloomy relationship between intensity severe score and emotional maturity. The co-efficient of correlation between intensity severe score and directionality score in externalizing is 0.74. Thus, there is positive but high relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between intensity severe score and directionality score in internalizing; a dimension of behavioural problem is 0.60. That infers there is positive but high relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between intensity severe score and frequency score is - 0.13. Thus there is negative and low comparison. The co-efficient of correlation between total behavioural problem and emotional stability is - 0.05. So, there is adverse but negligible relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between total behavioural problem and emotional progression, a dimension of emotional maturity is - 0.06. That indicates that there is negative but negligible relationship. The co-efficient of correlation between total behavioural problem and social adjustment is 0.05. That refers there is positive but negligible relationship between behavioral problem and social adjustment. The co-efficient of correlation between total behavioural problem and personality integration is 0.10. Thence, there is positive but negligible relationship. The co-efficient of correlation

between total behavioural problem and independence is 0.19. That shows that there is positive but negligible interrelation. The co-efficient of correlation between total behavioural problem and total emotional maturity is 0.04. That indicates that there is positive but very negligible interconnection. The co-efficient of correlation between total behavioural problem and directionality score of externality is 0.93. From here there is positive but very high relation. The co-efficient of correlation between total behavioural problem and directionality score of externality, a dimension of behavioural problem is 0.85. That means that there is positive but very high correlation between behavioral problem and internalizing behavioural problem. The co-efficient of correlation between total behavioural problem and frequency score is 0.54. That means that there is positive but marked correlation between behavioral problem and frequency behavioural problem. The co-efficient of correlation between total behavioural problem and intensity severe score, a dimension of behavioural problem is 0.77. That shows there is positive but very high correlation between behavioral problem and intensity severe behavioural problem.

XII. DISCUSSION:

Hypothesis 1 "Emotional maturity will be negatively correlated with behavioural problems and its dimensions". Table no 1 show that there is positive correlation between externalizing behavioral problem and emotional maturity. That means more mature adolescents show more externalizing problem behavior and vice versa. There is negative relationship between internalizing behavioral problem and emotional maturity. That means more emotionally mature adolescents' exhibit less internalizing problem behavior like self injurious behavior, repetitive behavior, odd behavior, hyperactivity and fears. Similarly less emotional mature person show more internalizing behavioural problem. There is positive relationship between frequency score of behavioral problem and emotional maturity. That means more mature adolescents exhibit more frequency behavior problem and vice-versa. There is positive relationship between intensity severe score of behavioral problem and emotional maturity. There is positive relationship between behavioral problem and emotional maturity.

Only one dimension of behavioural problem is negatively correlated with emotional maturity, Emotional maturity is positively correlated with behavioural problem and other three dimension of behavioural problem. But if we see the relationship between some dimensions of problem behavior and dimension of emotion maturity like direction score of externalizing with emotional stability and emotional

progression, there is negative relation. So, hypothesis 1 "emotional maturity will be negatively correlated with behavioural problem and its dimension" is partially accepted.

XIII. CONCLUSION:

From the findings it can be concluded that those adolescents are highly emotionally stable, they exhibit less externalizing problem behavior (violent destructive behavior, temper tantrum, misbehavior with others, rebellious behavior and antisocial behavior) and internalizing problem behavior (self injurious behavior, repetitive behavior, odd behavior, hyperactivity and fears). In contrary, less emotionally stable adolescents show more externalizing behavioural problem and internalizing behavioural problem. Adolescents having feelings of positive thinking of advancement and growing imbued with righteousness and contentment show more external and internal behaviour problem. So parents and teachers should try to develop positive thinking in adolescents towards their life, then behavior problem can be lessen in adolescent stage. Parents and teachers should keep eye on adolescents' emotional reaction whether swinging or stable. If swinging emotional reaction is noticed then gradually he/she should be practiced to react stable manner what is required for him/her in given situation, then only adolescent will lead a happy life without any depression and stress. Adolescents with good social adjustment exhibit less internalizing behavior like self injurious behavior, repetitive behavior, odd behavior, hyperactivity behavior and fears. In contrary, Adolescents having less social adjustment, they show more internalizing behavior. So teachers and parents should train adolescents how to cope with the society. Emotional mature adolescents exhibit more internalizing behavior problem and vice-versa. Adolescents having good social adjustment exhibit low frequency behavioural problem. Emotionally stable adolescents exhibit low intensity behavioural problem. Emotionally unstable adolescents show high intensity behavioral problem. Adolescents with positive thinking towards life show low intensity behavioral problem and vice-versa.

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